

APPROACHING THE STUDENT ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ROMANIA FROM A GENERATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Purpose – *Is to study the specific features of the Student entrepreneurship for generation Z from Romania.*

Methodology/approach - *The issue of entrepreneurship from the perspective of generational theory.*

Findings – *It is important in practice to use the characteristics of generation Z in entrepreneurship for the development of the national economy.*

Research limitations/implications – *Significant reduction in business start-ups by Generation Z students is a worrying economic phenomenon that needs immediate action to limit it.*

Practical implications – *It signals the decline of business start-ups by generation z students*

Originality/value – *Addressing entrepreneurship from a generational perspective*

Key words: *students, entrepreneurship, Generation Z*

Introduction

It is widely accepted that the entrepreneurship is considered the trigger of the current economies as it mobilizes, through innovation, a series of individual and group resources that have beneficial effects, quantifiable throughout the entire human society. According to Eurostat, in Romania, there are over 480,000 SMEs that employ nearly two-thirds of all employees. In the European Commission document "A strategy for SMEs for a sustainable and digital Europe" this idea is reconfirmed, being stated that "The 25 million small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Europe represent the backbone of the EU economy. They provide jobs for about 100 million people, representing more than half of Europe's GDP and play a key role in creating added value in each sector of the economy." (Eurobarometer, 2017)

Starting with 2020, the strategic orientation of the development of the sector of small and medium enterprises considers the double transition of the EU towards a sustainable and digital economy. The two orientations are part of the changing of the paradigm of economic development and are already present in the functioning of nearly one quarter of SMEs (including the social economy) in Europe which, in addition to high-tech, innovation and digitalization, respect the values of sustainability and circular economy offering green products or services.

Meanwhile, regarding these issues both from the perspective of generational theory and as a whole, the two European orientations – digitalization and sustainability – overlap the desires, options and characteristics of Generations Y and Z, with generations having the birth dates between 1977 and 1994 and between 1995 and 2012, respectively.

This study aims to examine the extent to which the entrepreneurial characteristics emphasized by the generational theory and results of entrepreneurship activities performed by students in Romania overlap.

Student Entrepreneurship in Romania

In Romania, as well as in the whole Europe, there are strategies for developing and strengthening the SME sector and, subsidiarily, constant concerns for stimulating the youth entrepreneurship. The government strategy for the development of small and medium enterprises is the central element of planning in this field, being built on five lines of action: the support of the entrepreneurship, SMEs' access to appropriate finance, SME access to abilities/skills and innovation, SMEs' access to markets and the government responsiveness to the needs of SMEs. To implement this strategy, a series of laws aimed at regulating the following areas have been issued: establishment and operation of SMEs, fiscality and access to SMEs financing, administrative simplification, regulation of labor relations.

To stimulate the entrepreneurship among students, the government issued, in 2003, the GD 166 regarding the granting of tax incentives to students who want to start their own business, a regulation that stipulates the exemption from fees and charges for start-ups in case of students who have business ideas and exploit them through entrepreneurship, by setting up their own company. This law provides exemptions from fees and charges to the National Trade Register Office, fees and charges for authorization of the tradesmen functioning requested when they found up the business, fees and charges necessary to obtain the authorization for self-employment from the local administration, taxes for publication in the Official Gazette of Romania and stamp duties for notary activity. These facilities are for all students enrolled at least in the second year of study in accredited higher education institutions who have fulfilled all the requirements and are under 30 years. For these entrepreneurs, the National Trade Register Office maintains separate accounts and follow them separately.

It is important to note that the stipulations of the GD 166/2003 are applicable for two generations, even since the beginning of their implementation. The two target generations are: Generation Y, with birth dates between 1977 and 1994 (with the proper age to access the law facilities between 2006 and 2013) and Generation Z, which is defined as the interval comprising dates of birth between 1995 and 2012 (with the maturity period comprising the years between 2013 and 2030, established for granting facilities).

Description of the research context

After the emergence of generational theory and until now, researchers in various fields of study, including marketing and human resource management have conducted several scientific studies aimed at the analysis and the more detailed knowledge of the characteristics and behaviours of the generational cohorts. From the human resources perspective, the studies have become more in-depth as generational groups have entered the labour market. At the same time, in correlation with the labour market, these researches were extended to the area of entrepreneurship.

In this study we started from the following premises:

- the analyzed period - between January 2014 and May 2020 is the period in which Generation Z exponents can be entrepreneurs and can exploit the provisions of GD 166/2003, i.e. they are at least 19 years old, are second year students in an accredited higher education institution, without arrears at the end of the first year and who have business ideas which they want to implement by setting up a company;
- in case they want to set up a company, they have to apply to the National Trade Register Office for their company registration, at which point they will also exploit the facilities offered by the normative act specified above; GD 166/2003 allows the reduction of the registration and authorization costs of the newly established companies by students by approximately 500 lei;
- at the same time, if the established company is no longer active, in order to avoid legal complications, tax, accounting etc. deriving from inactivity, the logic of things leads to the deregistration of the company, a process that is also carried out at the Trade Register;
- as a result, the statistical situations posted on the website of the National Trade Register Office starting with August 2013, offers a quantified image of the phenomenon of registration, but also of the deregistration of companies set up by students.

It is important to note that since the application of the government decision, the National Trade Register Office did not publish data on the effects of the application of GD 166/2003 until December 2012 when it published the fact that a number of 17,368 companies were set up by students, i.e. with a monthly average of the period of 147.19 companies. Of these, 4,901, i.e. 28.22% were deregistered (which represents a monthly average of deregistration of 42 companies in the period). At the end of 2013, the number of companies established according to GD 166/2003 was of 18,854 companies, which represents a monthly average for 2013 of 123.83 companies set up by students. Of these, 5,613 were deregistered, i.e. a monthly average of 59.33 companies. This demonstrates that since 2013 students have started to set up fewer and fewer companies, and accordingly, the facilities provided by law for them have been less and less used.

From the data published on the National Trade Register Office website, the number of companies established and deregistered by students, with the operation of the facilities offered by GD 166/2003, for the period December 2013 - May 2020, on semester intervals had an evolution described by Table 1. The reason for analysing this period is because starting with January 2014, the exponents of generation Z can enter the area of entrepreneurship (i.e. they are 19 years old, they are in the second year of university studies) and thus, they can benefit from the provisions of the government decision.

The graphical representation of the data in Table 1 is reflected in Figure 1.

Table 1 - Semi-annual evolution of the number of companies established and deregistered according to GD 166/2003 during December 2013 - May 2020

	Foundation	Deletion
2013 dec	150	335
2014 jun	250	455
2014 dec	136	429
2015 jun	176	444
2015 dec	101	535
2016 jun	95	638
2016 dec	60	466
2017 jun	50	352
2017 dec	27	385
2018 jun	35	316
2018 dec	24	311
2019 jun	22	324
2019 dec	26	244
2020 may	12	100

Corresponding to the evolution described in Figure 1, there is a sharp decrease in the number of companies set up and deregistered by students, but there are small increases for the first semester of each year, compared to the second semester of each year. It is important to note the following: if in December 2012 the percentage of deregistered companies out of the total of the existing ones was of 28.22%, in May 2020 this percentage reached 53.41%, i.e. almost doubling the deregistration, which led to the closure of more of the companies set up by students. Also, if between August and December 2013, the number of deregistered companies was 2.23 times higher than those established (335 deregistered companies and 150 established), between January and May 2020 this ratio was of 8.33 times (i.e. 100 companies deregistered and 12 established), which shows that the rate of deregistration compared to the establishment of companies increased almost 4 times between 2013 and 2020. At the same time, it is worth mentioning that, in the last part of 2018, the number of active companies became approximately equal to those of the deregistered ones. In May 2020, there were still 9,256 companies out of the 19,868 established by students according to GD 166/2003.

Figure 1. Semi-annual evolution of the number of companies established and deregistered according to GD 166/2003 during December 2013 - May 2020

Until August 2013, no data were published by the Trade Register, but interpreting the above data, it can be assumed that at the beginning of the period there was a slow, launching growth, specific to any process of this type. The launch was followed by an increase and then by a period of maturity which was highlighted until mid-2013. Since then and until now the process of granting tax facilities to students who wanted to set up their own business was in a steady decline, a situation confirmed by the current statistical data of the National Trade Register Office. According to them, starting with January 2017, less than 10 companies were set up every month in the whole country, in the first part of 2020 being a period of several months in which no company was set up to operate the facilities provided by GD 166/2003 (for the period March - May 2020 the Covid pandemic situation is a cause of limiting the establishment of companies, in March 2020 being established 3 companies, only one in April, and none in May).

A potential cause of the decline of business start-ups by students may be related to the increase in population income resulting from successive, more frequent and significant increases in the minimum wage in the economy since 2013. In this context, the amount of about 500 lei which is the value of facilities provided by law represented in January 2013 71.43%, while in January 2020 this share was less important, i.e. 22.42%. This also overlaps with the attitude and behaviour of students, elements that will be described below.

Generation Z – an entrepreneurial generation?

Theoretically, starting with 2017, the access to the facilities granted by GD 166/2003 can be exploited, in a considerable majority, only by the exponents of Generation Z. Exceptions may occur for students in Generation Y who started their university studies after 18 years, studies of faculties with a duration of more than three years, which repeat years of studies, etc. From 2018, the percentage of students in Generation Y becomes insignificant, i.e. Generation Z is the majority. At the same time, from 2018 until now, the period with the lowest number of companies set up by students is highlighted.

Several scientific studies have been conducted to analyze the characteristics of Generation Z from a psychological, sociological perspective, their behaviour on the labour market, their consumer perspective, their perceptions of various aspects of social life etc. So, starting from the general studies conducted by William Strauss and Neil Howe (1991) and William J. Schroer (2008) and reaching the newer research that targeted young people (entrepreneurs) at the global level (The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor - GEM), from European Union (European Start-up Monitor) or Romania (Public Opinion Barometer), they highlighted the characteristics of this generation, intentions, perceptions, worries, attitudes, lifestyle etc.

Thus, the members of Generation Z are called true "digital natives", almost half of them have smart phones and internet access, are multi-tasking and mobile, must have everything at a click away, are independent but also social (through social networks), visual (they like storytelling and are very attracted to influencers, youtubers and Instagram stories), they are global, they get bored easily. Also, an important feature is related to their more accentuated entrepreneurial and competitive spirit, given by their independence and at work they set their individual targets and they want that the reward be established following the individual performances not of the team, they prefer the flexible program and remote work, they do not like bosses but respect organizational hierarchies. In 2020, Generation Z represents 24% 4 of the global workforce.

Among the latest studies that targeted Generation Z, the research conducted by Ipsos MORI, called the IPF Financial Welfare Report, highlighted the fact that 53% of young people in Generation Z in Romania would like to open their own business, this being the highest percentage of countries analyzed.

Also, 61% of young people who participated in the study consider themselves more prepared for entrepreneurship than the previous generations. An important but also interesting result to follow is the one that shows that although they have all the openness to start up their own business, 67% of them claim that the current socio-economic context raises more barriers to entrepreneurs than in the past, and 55% of them consider that the difficult access to funding limits their opportunities to be more involved in the development of an entrepreneurial project.

These last aspects regarding the difficulties of entrepreneurs, but without direct connection with the generational theme, also result from the study of the EY Barometer 2019, 6th edition, which shows that 74% of the respondents consider that entrepreneurship is not supported by society, 52% consider that the fiscal and regulatory environment business deteriorated (8% more than in the study conducted in 2017), and in terms of measures that the state can take to stimulate the start-up business environment, 33% of entrepreneurs indicated the reduction or exemption of taxes and duties for start-ups and 27% mentioned financing solutions for this type of business. Also, the biggest obstacle is considered to be the mentality and the fear of failure (20%) and 22% consider that the school / university does not prepare them to be entrepreneurs.

Conclusions

Throughout the world, entrepreneurship is a strong force for economic development and the orientation of the young Generations Y and Z towards entrepreneurship mobilizes and directs towards the economy, with quantifiable results, the innovative and entrepreneurial spirit that characterizes them.

Combining the information from the analysis carried out on the companies set up by students since 2003 up to the present with the capitalization of the provisions of GD 166/2003 (on granting fiscal facilities to students wishing to set up their own business) and the studies carried out by specialized survey companies, the conclusions converge to that the entrepreneurial spirit of students, especially those of the Generation Z, is found in the intentions of establishing their own entrepreneurial career but these are not confirmed by the number of the established companies. This takes place in the conditions in which exemptions of taxes and tariffs are granted by legislation when students set up their own companies.

The main causes are in three directions:

- In the skills and individual development of Generation Z in Romania; by modification of the way in which young people are trained, in such a way as to give them self-confidence, to be oriented towards entrepreneurship etc.
- In the education system; in recent years, steps have been taken towards student entrepreneurship (Student Entrepreneurial Societies and the financing of programs to support entrepreneurship), but there are still many ways in which things can change in this direction;
- In the current economic and legislative environment; In these areas, measures are needed to lead to fiscal predictability, state funding for development, promotion of start-up financing programs, facilitating access to finance etc.

All these topics can be the subject of separate research through which it will be possible to establish concrete ways to reach the goal - to capitalize on the entrepreneurial potential of Generation Z.

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